

Viscosity of Solutions of Cadmium Sulphate in Aqueous Acetic Acid

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A number of studies on viscosity of aqueous and non-aqueous solutions have appeared¹⁻⁵. In recent years, work has been carried out for viscosity of 1:1 electrolytes in many non-aqueous solvents like DMSO⁶, formamide⁷, nitromethane⁸, diethylene glycol⁹, N,N-dimethyl formamide¹⁰, acetone¹¹ and sulfolane¹² and their water mixtures. Most recently, the thermodynamic and transport properties of low molecular weight organic acids (particularly carboxylic acids) and their metal complexes, have been recognised as important constituent of oil-field and geothermal water studies. Acid and metal-complexes equilibria involving these species may substantially influence mineral equilibria in surface waters. However such type of studies have received very little attention. In particular not even a single detailed study of 2:2 electrolytes in aqueous acetic acid has been noticed so far. The objective of the present communication is to report data for 2:2 electrolyte (cadmium sulphate) in aqueous acetic acid from viscosity measurements. The results have been interpreted in terms of Jones Dole equation¹³. The variation of B coefficient of Jones Dole equation has been studied with respect to different compositions of aqueous acetic acid and different temperatures.

Experimental

Cadmium sulphate (AnalaR) was used without further purification, after drying over anhydrous CaCl₂. Water of specific conductance of the order of 10⁻⁶ ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ was used for making, by mass, the aqueous mixtures of acetic acid. Acetic acid (GR) was purified by distillation. All solutions were made by weight and conversion of molality to molarity was done by using the expression¹⁴.

$$C = \frac{d \cdot m \cdot 1000}{1000 + m M_2}$$

where C is the molarity, d the density of solution, m the molality and M₂ the molecular weight of cadmium sulphate. Density was measured with an apparatus similar to the one reported by Ward and Millero and described elsewhere¹⁵. The viscosity was measured with the help of a capillary type viscometer¹⁶. Triple distilled water was used as a standard liquid, and the viscosity coefficient of water used for calculations were 0.8937 × 10⁻², 0.8007 × 10⁻² and 0.7225 × 10⁻² poise at 25, 30, 35°, respectively. The accuracy of the experiment was checked by measuring the viscosity of benzene at 25° and the value was found to be 0.5994 × 10⁻²

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poise which was in agreement with the literature value¹⁷ of 0.5996 × 10⁻² poise.

Results and Discussion

It has been found by a number of workers that the addition of electrolyte could either break or make the structure of a liquid. Since viscosity is a property of liquids which depends upon the intermolecular forces, the structural aspects of liquids can be inferred from the viscosity of solutions at different concentrations and temperatures. With the development of interionic theory, much of the interest in the subject has been directed towards accurate determination of the viscosity of very dilute solutions of electrolytes and theoretical interpretation of the results.

Density, viscosity and relative viscosity of cadmium sulphate in different compositions of aqueous acetic acid at 25° were determined and the same parameters have also been obtained for 20% acetic acid at 25, 30, 35°. The values obtained are reported in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

TABLE 1—DENSITY, VISCOSITY AND RELATIVE VISCOSITY OF CADMIUM SULPHATE AT 25° IN DIFFERENT COMPOSITIONS OF AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID

Conc. of cadmium sulphate C × 10 ³ (Mol. l ⁻¹)	Density (g. cm ⁻³)	Viscosity η × 10 ³ poise	Relative Viscosity η/η ₀
0% Acetic acid η ₀ = 0.8937 × 10 ⁻² poise			
1.99	1.0021	0.9252	1.0353
3.99	1.0071	0.9473	1.0600
5.98	1.0121	0.9675	1.0826
7.97	1.0170	0.9884	1.1060
9.96	1.0220	0.0069	1.1267
10% Acetic acid η ₀ = 1.0517 × 10 ⁻² poise			
4.10	1.0378	1.0903	1.0367
5.13	1.0395	1.1009	1.0468
6.15	1.0411	1.1087	1.0542
7.17	1.0433	1.1193	1.0643
8.19	1.0455	1.1297	1.0742
10.22	1.0484	1.1540	1.0973
20% Acetic acid η ₀ = 1.1906 × 10 ⁻² poise			
2.04	1.0282	1.2105	1.0167
3.06	1.0289	1.2252	1.0291
5.10	1.0331	1.2517	1.0513
6.11	1.0347	1.2646	1.0622
7.13	1.0381	1.3028	1.0942
10.19	1.0461	1.3221	1.1104
30% Acetic acid η ₀ = 1.2467 × 10 ⁻² poise			
1.03	1.0354	1.2557	1.0072
3.09	1.0395	1.2762	1.0237
4.12	1.0423	1.2838	1.0298
5.15	1.0451	1.2976	1.0408
6.19	1.0478	1.3098	1.0506
8.24	1.0534	1.3514	1.0840
9.78	1.0561	1.3661	1.0958
10.32	1.0589	1.3830	1.1093
40% Acetic acid η ₀ = 1.5064 × 10 ⁻² poise			
2.08	1.0433	1.5295	1.0153
3.03	1.0509	1.5484	1.0279
4.17	1.0535	1.5612	1.0364
5.15	1.0566	1.5924	1.0571
6.25	1.0598	1.6240	1.0781
7.25	1.0628	1.6591	1.1014
8.32	1.0659	1.6365	1.1086

TABLE 2—DENSITY, VISCOSITY AND RELATIVE VISCOSITY OF CADMIUM SULPHATE IN 20% ACETIC ACID AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Conc. of cadmium sulphate $C \times 10^2$ (mol. l ⁻¹)	Density d (g. cm ⁻³)	Viscosity $\eta \times 10^3$ poise	Relative Viscosity η/η_0
Temp. 25°; $\eta_0 = 1.1906 \times 10^{-2}$ poise			
2.04	1.0292	1.2105	1.0167
3.06	1.0289	1.2252	1.0291
5.10	1.0331	1.2517	1.0513
6.11	1.0347	1.2646	1.0622
7.13	1.0381	1.3028	1.0942
10.19	1.0461	1.3221	1.1104
Temp. 30°; $\eta_0 = 1.0645 \times 10^{-2}$ poise			
2.09	1.0237	1.0664	1.0018
4.17	1.0281	1.0845	1.0188
6.25	1.0336	1.1046	1.0377
8.33	1.0395	1.1274	1.0591
10.38	1.0503	1.1493	1.0797
Temp. 35°; $\eta_0 = 0.9198 \times 10^{-2}$ poise			
2.02	1.0219	0.9356	1.0172
4.13	1.0265	0.9653	1.0495
6.56	1.0331	1.0037	1.0912
8.01	1.0376	1.0376	1.1146
11.13	1.0483	1.0737	1.1673

TABLE 3—VALUES OF PARAMETERS A AND B OF JONES DOLE EQUATION FOR CADMIUM SULPHATE IN DIFFERENT COMPOSITION OF ACETIC ACID AT 25°

System	A	B
Cadmium sulphate in 0% acetic acid	+0.13	+0.85
Cadmium sulphate in 10% acetic acid	-0.04	+1.12
Cadmium sulphate in 20% acetic acid	-0.06	+1.33
Cadmium sulphate in 30% acetic acid	-0.16	+1.50
Cadmium sulphate in 40% acetic acid	-0.19	+2.04

Temperature effect: The parameters A and B of Jones Dole equation have also been calculated from the straight line plots of $\eta/\eta_0 - 1/\sqrt{C}$ vs \sqrt{C} for 20% acetic acid at different temperatures. The corresponding values are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF PARAMETERS A AND B JONES DOLE EQUATION FOR 20% ACETIC ACID AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temperature °C	A	B
25	-0.067	+1.29
30	-1.170	+1.48
35	-1.170	+1.88

It is observed that values of viscosities of cadmium sulphate solution in water and different compositions of aqueous acetic acid increase with increasing concentration of the electrolyte and decrease with increasing temperatures. It is further found that a linear relation between relative viscosity and square root of concentration exists. So, plots of η/η_0 vs \sqrt{C} should be straight line according to Falkenhagen-Dole equation¹⁸

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + S_{(\eta)} \sqrt{C}$$

where $S_{(\eta)}$ is the limiting slope. It is found that Falkenhagen-Dole theory is valid in concentration range reported here in all mixtures of aqueous acetic acid. The viscosity data have been analysed by means of Jones Dole equation¹⁹

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC$$

where C is the molar concentration and A is a constant representing the contribution from inter-ionic electrostatic forces²⁰. B coefficient is an adjustable parameter either positive or negative and is said to be a measure of the effective hydrodynamic volume of solvated ions that accounts for ion-solvent interaction²¹. It is also a measure of order or disorder introduced by ions into the solvent structure. The values of A and B coefficients have been determined from the intercept and slope of the straight line plots of $\eta/\eta_0 - 1/\sqrt{C}$ vs \sqrt{C} in the different mixtures of aqueous acetic acid at 25° and are reported in Table 3.

According to Table 3, the B coefficient increases whereas the A coefficient decreases with the increase in acid content. The increase in the value of B parameter suggests that more of ions enter into the void space of the solvent thereby introducing more of order.

The positive B coefficient in different compositions of aqueous acetic acid and at different temperatures can be attributed to large size of ion. It has been emphasized by a number of workers that dB/dT is a more important criterion²² for determining the solute-solvent interactions. Viscosity study of a number of such solutions has shown that structure-makers will have negative values of dB/dT and structure-breakers positive values. Accordingly, the positive temperature coefficient of B in this case suggests that cadmium sulphate behaves like structure-breaker. This is in accordance with our earlier conclusion from the study of molar volumes of cadmium sulphate¹⁵.

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Chemical Constituents of *Verbesina encelioides* and *Holmskioldia sanguinea*

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VERBESINA encelioides (Cav) (Compositae) is a much branched tall herb. It was collected from the Rajasthan University campus, Jaipur, and a voucher specimen was deposited in Rajasthan University Botany Laboratories herbarium via sheet No. 12977. A perusal of literature revealed that some work has been reported on the species¹⁻⁴. The present work deals with the chemical examination of its aerial parts and roots separately. *Holmskioldia sanguinea* (Retz) (Verbenaceae) is a struggling shrub, 10-30 feet in height. It was obtained from the United Chemical and Allied Products, Calcutta. No work has been done so far on *H. sanguinea*, and therefore, we undertook the chemical investigation of the plant.

Experimental

Verbesina encelioides: Air dried and coarsely powdered roots and aerial parts (1.5 kg each) were

extracted separately with petroleum ether-ether (2 : 1) mixture in cold for 12 hr. The extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure and chromatographed over silica gel. Fractions collected were purified over preparative silica gel glass plates using various solvents mixture as eluants. Following compounds were identified by spectral and chemical studies as well as by comparison with authentic samples.

Results and Discussion

Bornyl ferulate: It is an oily liquid and its molecular formula $C_{20}H_{28}O_4$ was established by high resolution mass spectrometry. MS: m/e 330 (M^+). IR $\nu_{max}^{CCl_4}$: 3470 (OH stretch), 1715 (unsaturated C=O stretch) cm^{-1} . 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 6.30 (1H, d, J=16 Hz), 7.60 (1H, d, J=16 Hz) for $-CH=CH$ trans olefinic protons; 7.05 (1H, d, J=2 Hz), 7.07 (1H, dd, J=8.5, 2 Hz), 6.9 (1H, d, J=8.5 Hz) for 3 aromatic protons; 3.92 (3H, s, OCH_3 group), 5.00 [1H, d(br), C-2 proton], 0.93 (3H, s, C-7 Me), 0.89 (3H, s, C-9 Me), 0.88 (3H, s, C-10 Me), multiplets at 1.05, 1.6, 2.05, 2.4 ppm due to 3, 3', 4, 5, 5', 6 and 6' protons of bornyl ring. These data agree with the reported ones⁵. It was finally confirmed by comparing its nmr with that of an authentic sample.

Linolenic and linoleic acids were identified by preparation of their methyl esters⁶.

Taraxasterol acetate, α - and β -amyriins, stigmasterol and β -sitosterol gave positive tests for triterpenoids and sterols and were identified by preparation of their acetyl derivatives and comparison with authentic samples.

Benzyl-2,6-dimethoxy benzoate: It is a colourless liquid and its high resolution mass spectrometry (M^+ 272) established its molecular formula $C_{16}H_{16}O_4$. IR $\nu_{max}^{CCl_4}$ cm^{-1} : 1750 (C=O stretch of ester group), 1610, 1590 ($-C=CH$ stretch, aromatic). 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 3.8 (6H, s, $2 \times OCH_3$ group), 5.37 (2H, s, benzylic protons), 6.55 (2H, d, J=8.5 Hz, C-3, 5 protons), 7.26 (1H, d, J=8.5 Hz, C-4 proton), 7.44 (2H, dd, J=8.5, 1.5 Hz, C-2', 6' protons) and 7.36 (3H, m, C-3', 4', 5' protons). These data agree with the reported values and was finally confirmed by comparing its nmr with that of an authentic material⁷.

Phytol: It is a colourless liquid, MS: m/e 296 (M^+) corresponded to its molecular formula $C_{20}H_{40}O$. IR $\nu_{max}^{CCl_4}$ cm^{-1} : 3656-3580 (O-H stretch). 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 5.14 [1H, t (br), $=CH-CH_2OH$], 4.16 (2H, dd, CH_2OH protons), 0.86, 0.87, 0.88, 0.89 (3H each d, J=7 Hz, C-7, 11, 16, 17 methyl protons), 1.67 (3H, s, C-3 Me protons). These data agree with its structure and finally confirmed by preparation of its acetate (M^+ 338)⁸.